

Artificial Intelligence at ArianeGroup: activities and stakes

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The integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies within ArianeGroup processes is revolutionizing various aspects of our operations. This paper presents an overview of how we are implementing AI solutions to enhance performance in space launchers development, manufacturing and operations, as well as developing new services such as Space Situational Awareness (SSA). We also present our challenges in the development of internal artificial intelligence towards processes optimization, in terms of technology bricks, company organization and conformity with regulation bodies.

The stakes for the future are significant, with potential improvements in cost efficiency, reliability, and innovation. By leveraging cutting-edge AI technologies, ArianeGroup aims to maintain its position as a leading player in the global space industry while contributing to advancements in sustainable space exploration. As we continue to explore new applications of AI within our organization, we remain committed to fostering collaboration with academic institutions and space agencies to drive innovation and ensure responsible use of these technologies.

1 Introduction

ArianeGroup has always been analyzing data, and using state-of-the-art techniques to do so. In this spirit, our first neural networks were developed in the 1990s to analyze engine tests data. With the exponential development of AI techniques within the company, we structured the Data Analytics and Artificial Intelligence discipline in 2018 as one of our core competencies.

Since then, we observe an approximate 30% growth of AI activities each year, that are split between small centralized data scientists teams, and experts spread within business teams with double competencies (e.g. space situational awareness, guidance navigation and control...).

Our strategy is not to compete with big tech companies on AI, but to master the key competencies which will be game changers for our activities. As such, we have two ways of adding AI bricks into processes: either from a functional need expressed by businesses

(e.g. need of reactivity in health monitoring systems), or by pushing new technologies offering new capabilities (e.g. large language models to assist knowledge management).

2 Results

2.1 Application to space launchers

ArianeGroup is mainly known for its space launcher Ariane 6, to secure heavy-lift access to space at European level. Regarding these products, ArianeGroup coordinates all activities from research and technology development, design, development, series production, final integration and launch campaign preparation, and operational services (as assistant to Arianespace). In all of these operations, there are already some forms of AI embedded in our processes.

2.1.1 Launchers development

In launcher development phases, our focus is toward building surrogate models on simulated data or operational data from past products. Our objectives are to specify products at the right probabilistic level, propagate uncertainties to improve margin knowledge, and understand better systems through sensitivity analysis and optimization. The techniques behind these activities rely mostly on non-deep machine learning algorithms such as Gaussian processes. We are also investigating more complex methods to assist topology optimization, and compute aerodynamics or thermal flows with physics-informed neural networks. However, at this stage the robustness of the methods does not allow to replace more time-consuming but more reliable techniques.

The figure 1 shows an example of Ariane 6 upper stage reentry aerodynamic flows. The results are generated in 3 milliseconds, compared to several hours for a similar result with traditional CFD. But, the precision on protrusions is below our expectations, and explainability tools to understand how the neural networks makes the difference between macro flows and local

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Figure 1: Ariane 6 upper stage reentry aerodynamics flow computed with a physics-informed neural network

Figure 2: Automated defect detection in additive layer manufacturing processes

phenomena do not allow to clarify how to define a sufficient training set.

2.1.2 Launchers production

On production lines, our objective is to reduce costs and lead times, with a target of twelve launchers per year for Ariane 6. These numbers remain relatively small compared to other industries, as well as the volume of data available for training models. We focus on production processes monitoring, to perform predictive quality by detecting defects in real time [1], and therefore reduce the needs for controls as we can target pre-detected phenomena. With the same sensors, we can also detect performance drifts along time and perform predictive maintenance.

The figure 2 shows a layer of additive manufacturing process in liquid engine parts, seen in infrared bandwidths. The neural network is trained to recognize defects on past data, and learns to identify future ones with an impressive false positive rate of 0.01% while detecting all defects from the test dataset.

Real-time monitoring of the geolocation of mobile means (e.g. containers, vehicles), when merged with scheduling data, allows to detect delays and re-plan activities in an optimal way. When analyzing a longer period of activity, we can also analyze the patterns of flows and associated activities, to suggest optimizations. [2]

Figure 3: Novelty detected in flight data

2.1.3 Launchers operations

In all the operational data (engine tests or flights), we can use machine learning systems to learn nominal behavior of systems based on an history, and isolate abnormal behaviors in latter tests or flights. The key gain of AI in those systems is that it can take into account thousands of different sensors, and infer the impact of each command or external factor on the launcher, to isolate the rare occurrences of a different reaction from a system to a given environment. Figure 3 shows an example of learnt behavior on a pressure sensor, and its comparison to operational data allowing anomaly detection. It simplifies the data exploitation phase by focusing more quickly on the most important abnormal phenomena.

Onboarding AI is the next step for years to come. This raises specific challenges such as reactivity, compatibility with flight hardware, certification with tutoring agencies. Our work focuses on new-generation health monitoring systems, which would be especially useful on multi-engines reusable launchers. In guidance, navigation and control, AI can also help manage complex phenomena such as propellant sloshing in low-gravity [3] or landing phases.

2.2 Other applications

2.2.1 Knowledge management

As the historical European stakeholder of space launches, ArianeGroup has decades of history of technical documentation. Its value is multiplied by quick and easy access tools, such as large language models combined with retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) systems. It helps retrieve and synthesize information from the past, but also speed up consistency analysis and impact assessment of a change on a system, including updating the documentation itself. This branch of AI is particular as it is directly accessible by

all ArianeGroup collaborators, which implies a strong need for user support, and security in access to information. The performance of retrieval-augmented generation also depends on the understanding of the user's request by the system, which raises challenge in the structure of the company knowledge. The link with models used in system engineering (e.g. functional or architectural graphs) is a strong axis for progress in this field.

2.2.2 New services

With the help of AI, we can go deeper into analysis of the data collected by our Helix™ stations, watching the sky from all around the globe. It makes us capable of tracking thousands of objects on all orbits, analyze their behavior, and anticipate collisions with debris. ArianeGroup can therefore provide its clients with more services, with reduced response time.

3 Challenges

3.1 Technological

ArianeGroup faces several technological challenges in leveraging Artificial Intelligence (AI) to enhance its operations. One of the primary concern is the limited availability of datasets, which makes it difficult to validate AI models in critical applications where uncertainty management is key.

Ensuring that AI systems are robust and explainable is crucial, as opacity can lead to mistrust and errors. Another challenge lies in monitoring performance drifts once AI models are deployed into production, where they may be exposed to new, unforeseen data patterns. Onboard AI systems require smaller, faster models that can operate efficiently on new hardware yet to be validated.

3.2 Organization

Our focus is hiring and training a workforce with the necessary skills to develop, implement, and maintain AI systems. Additionally, governance and IT infrastructure must undergo substantial changes to accommodate AI, which can be a complex and time-consuming process. Ensuring data access control while breaking down silos is also crucial, as it enables collaboration while maintaining security and integrity. ArianeGroup must also prioritize a human-centric approach, empowering employees with large language models that enhance their capabilities rather than replacing them. The company must also find a delicate balance between achieving quick results

through AI, and spending more time on more classical methods, which provides a deeper understanding of the underlying physics principles and ensures long-term robustness.

3.3 Legal

ArianeGroup faces a range of legal challenges as it integrates Artificial Intelligence (AI) into its operations. One of the most pressing concerns is obtaining certification for on-board AI systems in critical applications, which requires meeting stringent safety and reliability standards. The company must also navigate the complex regulatory landscape surrounding AI, including ensuring compliance with personal data management regulations such as GDPR. Furthermore, ArianeGroup needs to establish standardized practices internally and align them with those of external bodies like ECSS (European Cooperation for Space Standardization) and DGA (French Directorate General of Armaments), which will facilitate collaboration and ensure consistency across the industry. Finally, the company must protect its intellectual property while delivering AI models and/or training datasets, a delicate balancing act that requires careful consideration of contractual agreements and data sharing protocols.

4 Conclusion

In conclusion, ArianeGroup's integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies has revolutionized various aspects of our operations in space launchers development, manufacturing, and operations. We have demonstrated the potential of AI to enhance performance, reduce costs, and improve reliability across multiple applications. However, we also acknowledge the challenges that come with developing internal artificial intelligence capabilities, including technological, organizational, and legal aspects.

Ultimately, our goal is to harness the power of AI to create a safer, more efficient, and more innovative space industry.

References

1. Camps, M. *et al.* in (Oct. 2021). ISBN: 9781643682105.
2. Liberati, F., Tortorelli, A., Mazquiaran, C., Imran, M. & Panfili, M. *Optimal Control of Industrial Assembly Lines in 2020 7th International Conference on Control, Decision and Information Technologies (CoDIT) 1* (2020), 721–726.
3. Cocaul, P., Piet-Lahanier, H., Ganet, M., Bertrand, S. & Lemazurier, L. *Anti Sloshing Control Law Design For Launchers Using A Model-Free Approach in EUCASS-3AF 2022 (LILLE, France, June 2023)*. <https://hal.science/hal-03944575>.